

Reactivity of the Binuclear Compound, $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ ($\text{Cp} = \eta^5\text{-Cyclopentadienyl}$, $\text{Ph} = \text{Phenyl}$) and Synthesis of Higher Nuclear Compounds

RAJIB LAL DE*, PROSENJIT BISWAS and TARIT ROYCHOWDHURY

Department of Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 1 July 1991, revised 21 November 1991, accepted 27 January 1992

The dehydrogenation reaction of $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ with $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$, $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$, $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $\text{CpMn}(\text{CO})_5$ were performed both in benzene and toluene medium and the compounds $\text{CpCo}_2(\text{CO})_6(\mu_2\text{-PPh})$ and $\text{Cp}_2\text{Co}_4(\text{CO})_{12}(\mu_2\text{-CO})(\mu_4\text{-PPh})_2$ along with few other already known products were isolated. The compounds were characterised by elemental analysis, ir, ^1H nmr and mass spectral studies

The compounds, $\text{LnMCo}_2(\text{CO})_7(\text{PPh})$ (**1**)¹ were formed ($\text{LnM} = \text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$, $\text{Mo}(\text{CO})_6$ and $\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$) when the phosphine complexes, LnMPPhH_2 were allowed to react with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$. The reaction of LnMPPhH_2 , where $\text{LnM} = \text{CpMn}(\text{CO})_5$ with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$, took a different course and led to the formation of a binuclear compound, $\text{CpMnCo}(\text{CO})_5\text{PPhH}$ (**2**)¹.

The binuclear compound (**2**) with the hydrogen atom present on phosphorus provides potentiality of further dehydrogenation reaction with suitable metal carbonyls and under suitable reaction conditions may lead to the synthesis of a variety of compounds with enhancement in nuclearity.

Dehydrogenation reaction of **2** by four different metal carbonyls, e.g. $\text{Fe}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$, $\text{Ru}_3(\text{CO})_{12}$, $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ and $\text{CpCo}(\text{CO})_2$ have been investigated with a view to explore the possible formation of mixed metal clusters of enhanced nuclearity.

Results and Discussion

The solutions of compound **2** and the metal carbonyls were first mixed at room temperature and as revealed by the ir spectra at ν_{CO} region, no reaction took place even after 24 h. Appreciable reaction however took place at higher temperatures. In boiling benzene, trinuclear species were mainly formed, whereas the tetranuclear species were the main products in boiling toluene medium. The reactions were found to go into completion within 3-4 h and on prolonged heating the products started decomposing as evidenced by the slow disappearance of ν_{CO} bands in the ir spectra. The

products were separated from each other and from other undesired materials by column chromatography. Final purifications were achieved by crystallisation.

In benzene medium, **3a-d** were solid products. **3a** and **3b** formed easily and with some better yields than reported². The tetranuclear cobalt cluster **3c** was obtained in small amount. Better methods are available for its preparation³. Formation of **3c**, among other products were also observed when the compounds LnMPPhH_2 were brought into reaction with $\text{Co}_2(\text{CO})_8$ ⁴. The cluster **3d** was isolated as a dark-brown crystalline solid.

3a, $\text{M} = \text{Fe}$
3b; $\text{M} = \text{Ru}$

In toluene medium, besides **3a-d**, another compound **4** was isolated as a crystalline solid. The yields of **3a**, **3b** and **3d** were lower in toluene than in benzene medium whereas that of **3c** increased to some extent. The cluster **4** was isolated as black crystals.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd	Colour	M p. °C	Mol. formula (Mol wt)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)			ν_{CO} cm^{-1}	δ (Cp)	δ (Ph)
				C	H	Co			
3d	Dark brown	121-22	$C_{17}H_{10}Co_4O_4$ (518.0)	38.78 (36.42)	1.89 (1.94)	33.68 (34.18)	2 096w, 2 038s 2 029vs, 1 999w	4.78	7.46 (m)
4	Black	192-93d	$C_{27}H_{20}Co_4O_8P_2$ (722.1)	45.12 (44.91)	2.66 (2.79)	31.08 (32.64)	2 091w, 2 046vs, 2 028s, 1 869m	4.56	7.58 (m)

The formation of the tetranuclear compound 4 in boiling toluene ratifies the fact that higher nuclear cluster formation usually needs application of more vigorous conditions and also the reluctance of manganese to enter into the cluster framework.

In the ir spectra, ν_{CO} frequencies were found to be within the expected range (2 200–2 000 cm^{-1}) and indicated the presence of only terminal CO groups in 3d. The presence of an additional ν_{CO} band in lower region of the spectrum (1 900–1 850 cm^{-1}) in case of 4 clearly indicated the presence of CO groups bridged between the two cobalt atoms (Table 1). The 1H nmr spectra indicated the presence of cyclopentadienyl (δ 4.5–4.8) and the phenyl groups (δ 7.4–7.6 multiplet) for compounds 3d and 4 (Table 1).

The overall simplicity and the presence of only sharp bands in the ν_{CO} region of the ir spectra suggest high symmetry of the molecules of the compounds 3d and 4. The 1H nmr spectra showed the appearance of a singlet in the cyclopentadienyl region and the presence of the two CpCo-groups as *cis* to each other is being proposed for compound 4. Results of elemental analyses and molecular weight determinations by mass spectroscopic methods agreed well with their formulations (Table 1).

Experimental

All handlings were performed under nitrogen atmosphere. The organic solvents used were dried and distilled. Silica gel 60 was made water-free at 160° under reduced pressure before use for column chromatography.

The title compound 2 was prepared by the method reported earlier¹. $Fe_2(CO)_9$ ⁵, $Co_2(CO)_8$ ⁶,

$CpMn(CO)_5$ ⁶ and the phosphine PPh_3 ⁷ were prepared by the literature methods. $Ru_3(CO)_{12}$ and $CpCo(CO)_2$ were used as such.

Ir spectra (CH_2Cl_2) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectrophotometer and 1H nmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) on a Varian T-60A (60 MHz) apparatus using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded by Dr. Alfred Bernhardt's Laboratory, Germany. C and H analyses were performed at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Cobalt contents were estimated by the spectrophotometric method.

Reactions of 2 with the metal carbonyls :

In benzene medium : Compound 2 (1.5 mmol) and the metal carbonyls (1.5 mmol) were mixed in benzene (30 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled to room temperature, the volume reduced to 5 ml under reduced pressure and chromatographed on a silica gel column. The fractions collected by eluting with *n*-hexane-toluene (10 : 1), on removal of all solvents and recrystallisation from *n*-hexane yielded compounds 3a–d as crystalline solids : $HFe_2Co(CO)_9(\mu_2-PPh)$ (3a ; 0.55 g, 65%), $HRu_3Co(CO)_9(\mu_3-PPh)$ (3b ; 0.74 g, 74%), $Co_4(CO)_{10}(\mu_2-CO)_2(\mu_4-PPh)_2$ (3c ; 0.38 g, 28%), $CpCo_3(CO)_8(\mu_3-PPh)$ (3d ; 0.17 g, 19%).

In toluene medium : Compound 2 (1.5 mmol) and the metal carbonyls (1.5 mmol) were mixed in toluene (30 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled to room temperature, the volume reduced to 5 ml under reduced pressure and chromatographed on a silica gel column. Fraction-1 collected by eluting with *n*-hexane-toluene (10 : 1), on removal of all solvents and recrystallisation from *n*-hexane yielded compounds 3a–d as crystalline products : 3a (0.38 g, 44%), 3b (0.39 g, 39%), 3c (0.27 g, 24%), 3d (0.11 g, 12%). Fraction-2 collected by eluting with *n*-hexane-toluene (5 : 1), on removal of all solvents and recrystallisation from *n*-hexane-chloroform (8 : 1) yielded 4 as a crystalline product : $Cp_2Co_4(CO)_4(\mu_2-CO)(\mu_4-PPh)_2$ (0.23 g, 21%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the authority, Jadavpur University, for providing a special research grant to them.

DE, BISWAS & ROYCHOWDHURY : REACTIVITY OF THE BINUCLEAR COMPOUND *etc.*

References

- 1 R. L. DE and H VAHRENKAMP *Z Naturforsch , Teil B* 1985, **40**, 1250
- 2 M MULLER and H VAHRENKAMP, *Chem Ber* 1983 **116** 2311
3. R. C RYAN and L. F. DAHL, *J. Am Chem Soc* , 1975 **97**, 6904 . BIAN-HUNG CHANG, *Inorg Chim Acta* 1982, **65** L89
- 4 R L DE, T. ROYCHOWDHURY and P BISWAS, Unpublished results
5. R B. KING in 'Organometallic Synthesis', eds J. J EISCH and R B. KING, Academic, New York, 1965.
- 6 R L. DE Dr. Rer nat Disseration, Freiburg University 1985
- 7 F PASS, E STEININGER and H ZORN, *Monatsh Chem* 1982 **93** 280